

Toward Integrated IAQ Monitoring in Hospitals: Integrating Continuous Monitoring, Chemical Characterization, Airborne Microbiome, and Time-Resolved Analysis

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Abstract

Indoor air quality (IAQ) in healthcare environments is affected by dynamic interactions between occupancy, ventilation, operational activities, and indoor emission sources, which are not always captured through conventional punctual assessments. This study evaluated long-term IAQ dynamics in different hospital microenvironments using continuous low-cost sensor monitoring combined with targeted chemical characterization of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), specific aldehydes and airborne microbiome contextualization. Continuous monitoring was conducted from June 2023 to December 2025, measuring CO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, formaldehyde (CH₂O), temperature, relative humidity, and total VOCs (tVOCs). A total of 1.79 million raw records were processed, generating 1.42 million indoor measurements and 264,311 hourly aggregated observations. Complementary VOC and aldehyde sampling campaigns supported the interpretation of pollutant-specific temporal patterns. Results revealed differentiated IAQ behaviours across hospital areas. CO₂ dynamics were mainly associated with occupancy and ventilation demand, whereas formaldehyde showed more persistent accumulation patterns linked to continuous indoor emission sources and ventilation heterogeneity. Chemical characterization identified distinct pollutant signatures associated with cleaning activities, laboratory processes, occupancy, and ventilation conditions. The findings demonstrate that acceptable CO₂ levels do not necessarily indicate low chemical pollutant accumulation and support the use of continuous multi-parameter IAQ monitoring for more adaptive hospital IAQ management strategies.

Keywords: indoor air quality (IAQ), hospitals, continuous monitoring, low-cost sensors, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), formaldehyde, microbiome, healthcare environments, smart ventilation, building management systems (BMS).

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1. Introduction

Indoor air quality (IAQ) has become an increasingly important public health concern due to the large proportion of time spent indoors and the growing evidence linking indoor pollutant exposure with adverse health effects [1–3]. Healthcare facilities represent particularly sensitive indoor environments because they host vulnerable populations, including immunocompromised patients, elderly individuals, children, and healthcare workers subjected to prolonged occupational exposure [4–6]. In these environments, inadequate IAQ may contribute not only to discomfort and reduced wellbeing, but also to respiratory irritation, exacerbation of chronic diseases, increased susceptibility to infections, and impaired recovery processes [2,4]. Consequently, maintaining adequate IAQ conditions in hospitals is increasingly recognized as a critical component of preventive healthcare and healthy building strategies [5,7].

Hospital indoor environments are highly complex and dynamic systems characterized by heterogeneous occupancy patterns, diverse clinical and non-clinical activities, multiple pollutant sources, and continuously changing ventilation conditions [4,8]. Previous studies have shown that hospitals may contain elevated concentrations of particulate matter (PM), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), aldehydes, bioaerosols, and other airborne contaminants originating from outdoor infiltration, cleaning and disinfection products, medical procedures, building materials, occupant-related activities, and ventilation system operation [6,9–11]. In parallel, microbial communities present in hospital air are strongly influenced by occupancy levels, human activity, ventilation strategies, and spatial functionality, resulting in substantial variability between wards, waiting rooms, intensive care units (ICUs), operating theatres, and laboratories [12]. Such spatial and temporal heterogeneity makes IAQ characterization in healthcare environments particularly challenging [12].

Among indoor pollutants, VOCs and aldehydes have received increasing attention because of their widespread occurrence and potential health implications in healthcare environments [6,9]. These compounds may originate from cleaning and disinfection products, building materials, healthcare activities, laboratory procedures, occupant-related emissions, and consumer products, contributing to complex indoor chemical mixtures with highly variable temporal behaviour [6,9]. Formaldehyde is especially relevant due to its classification as a human carcinogen and its frequent presence in indoor settings associated with cleaning products, building materials, laboratory activities, and healthcare procedures [13]. Chronic exposure to formaldehyde and other volatile compounds has been associated with irritation symptoms, allergic responses, and long-term health risks, even at relatively low concentrations [13,14]. Recent occupational studies suggest that low-dose exposure may still produce measurable irritation-related and allergic symptoms despite concentrations remaining below conventional occupational exposure thresholds [14]. These findings reinforce the importance of monitoring strategies capable of detecting recurrent exposure events and pollutant accumulation patterns before guideline values are exceeded.

Despite the growing awareness of IAQ relevance in healthcare settings, conventional assessment approaches are still frequently based on punctual measurements, periodic inspections, or integrated sampling campaigns with limited temporal resolution [15,16]. Although these methodologies provide valuable chemical or microbiological characterization, they often fail to capture the strong short-term variability associated with occupancy dynamics, ventilation changes, cleaning activities, clinical operations, or episodic emission events [17]. Indoor environments are not static, and pollutant hotspots may vary substantially both spatially and temporally [18]. Consequently, averaged or discontinuous measurements may overlook transient exposure conditions that can be operationally and clinically relevant [17,18]. Moreover, relying exclusively on ventilation indicators such as

CO₂ may lead to incomplete interpretations of IAQ conditions, since acceptable CO₂ levels do not necessarily imply the absence of VOCs, aldehydes, or other chemically driven exposure scenarios [13].

Recent advances in low-cost sensing technologies, Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructures, cloud-based platforms, and smart building systems have enabled a paradigm shift in IAQ assessment toward continuous and high-resolution environmental monitoring [19–21]. Compared with traditional instrumentation, low-cost sensor (LCS) networks allow the deployment of distributed monitoring systems capable of generating continuous temporal information at much higher spatiotemporal resolution [18,22]. These systems facilitate the identification of recurrent exposure patterns, transient peaks, room-specific pollutant dynamics, and operational anomalies that would otherwise remain undetected using conventional episodic approaches [17,18]. Importantly, previous studies have demonstrated that, despite their limitations in absolute accuracy, properly calibrated and quality-controlled LCS systems can provide highly valuable information for environmental characterization, exposure assessment, and decision-support applications [19,20,23].

Beyond pollutant quantification itself, continuous monitoring opens the possibility of transforming IAQ assessment into an actionable and operational tool [21,24]. The integration of sensor networks with Building Management Systems (BMS), smart ventilation strategies, and data-driven environmental control approaches enables quasi-real-time interpretation of indoor environmental conditions and supports adaptive responses based on occupancy, pollutant peaks, or ventilation performance [24–26]. Recent studies have highlighted the potential of continuous IAQ monitoring to support predictive ventilation control, intelligent building operation, energy-efficient environmental management, and exposure-oriented interventions [24–27]. In this context, hospitals constitute especially relevant environments for the implementation of smart IAQ management strategies due to their operational complexity, high occupancy variability, and stringent environmental requirements.

Nevertheless, most existing studies remain focused either on sensor validation, isolated pollutant characterization, or proof-of-concept monitoring deployments, while practical frameworks capable of translating continuous IAQ monitoring into actionable hospital environmental management remain scarce [20,21]. Furthermore, continuous sensor monitoring alone may not fully explain pollutant sources, chemical composition, or biological context associated with observed temporal patterns. Complementary methodologies such as targeted chemical characterization and microbiome analysis can therefore provide essential contextual information for interpreting IAQ dynamics and identifying pollutant-specific operational signatures associated with different hospital environments and activities [9,12].

Within this context, the present study investigates indoor air quality dynamics in a hospital environment through the combined use of continuous low-cost IAQ monitoring, targeted chemical characterization, and microbiome analysis. The study aims not only to characterize pollutant variability and exposure patterns across different hospital areas, but also to evaluate how continuous monitoring systems can support operational IAQ management in healthcare facilities. Particular attention is given to the interpretation of time-resolved pollutant dynamics, pollutant-specific operational signatures, and the practical integration of IAQ monitoring networks into future BMS-oriented environmental management strategies. In this way, the work seeks to contribute to the ongoing transition from static IAQ assessment toward dynamic, data-driven, and health-oriented indoor environmental management frameworks for healthcare buildings.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design

This study was conducted at Hospital Clínic de Barcelona (HCB), a tertiary-care hospital located in Barcelona, Spain, within the framework of the K-HEALTHinAIR project. The aim was to perform a comprehensive multi-zone assessment of indoor air quality (IAQ) under real operating conditions by combining continuous monitoring with targeted chemical and biological characterization.

A longitudinal observational design was implemented between June 2023 and December 2025, enabling the characterization of IAQ dynamics across different seasons, occupancy conditions, and operational scenarios. The study integrated three complementary methodological approaches: (i) continuous real-time monitoring using low-cost sensor (LCS) devices, (ii) targeted sampling and chemical characterization of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and aldehydes, and (iii) airborne microbiome and bioaerosol characterization.

Monitoring was conducted across representative hospital microenvironments selected according to occupancy patterns, patient vulnerability, ventilation conditions, and potential pollutant sources. These included public spaces (main entrance hall and waiting areas), clinical environments (consultation rooms, hospitalization wards, and intensive care units), and technical or laboratory areas associated with potential chemical emissions. This multi-zone approach enabled the evaluation of IAQ under highly diverse operational conditions, ranging from controlled environments with advanced ventilation systems to highly dynamic occupancy-driven spaces.

Continuous monitoring focused on key IAQ indicators including carbon dioxide (CO₂), particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), formaldehyde (CH₂O), and total volatile organic compounds (tVOCs), providing high temporal resolution data for the identification of daily pollutant dynamics, recurrent exposure scenarios, and ventilation-related patterns. In parallel, targeted chemical and microbiological sampling campaigns were performed periodically to characterize indoor pollutant composition and airborne microbial communities.

The study design was specifically intended to support the integration of environmental, chemical, and biological datasets in order to identify operational IAQ signatures associated with occupancy, ventilation behaviour, pollutant sources, and hospital activities. Particular emphasis was placed on identifying actionable IAQ indicators capable of supporting real-time ventilation management and operational decision-making in healthcare environments.

2.2 Continuous Monitoring

Continuous IAQ monitoring was performed using commercially available low-cost sensor (LCS) devices (MICA Plus, inBiot, Spain), enabling high temporal resolution measurements under real hospital operating conditions. The monitoring systems incorporated sensors for carbon dioxide (CO₂), particulate matter (PM₁, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), formaldehyde (CH₂O), temperature, relative humidity, and total volatile organic compounds (tVOCs). CO₂ concentrations were measured using non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors and were primarily interpreted as indicators of occupancy-related ventilation demand. Particulate matter concentrations were estimated using optical particle counters based on light scattering principles, while formaldehyde was monitored using electrochemical sensors. tVOC measurements were obtained using metal-oxide (MOX) sensors and were interpreted qualitatively as indicators of volatile accumulation dynamics rather than quantitative measurements of specific compounds.

Although low-cost sensors present known limitations regarding selectivity, drift, and environmental sensitivity, they are increasingly recognized as valuable tools for continuous IAQ screening, temporal pattern identification, and operational ventilation

assessment in real-world environments [19–23]. Sensor reliability was further supported by previous validation studies performed under controlled and real indoor conditions using the same monitoring devices employed in this study [28]. In addition, periodic on-site checks using portable handheld instruments were conducted during field campaigns to qualitatively verify the consistency of selected measurements. Raw sensor datasets were processed using a reproducible Python-based workflow designed for harmonization, quality control, and temporal aggregation of the monitoring data. Processing steps included timestamp normalization, duplicate removal, indoor/outdoor separation, consistency checks, and generation of hourly aggregated datasets.

A total of 1.79 million raw records were processed, resulting in 1.42 million indoor measurements and 264,311 hourly aggregated observations covering the period from June 2023 to December 2025. Sensors were mapped to hospital zones, and their temporal representativeness was evaluated considering monitoring span, hourly coverage, seasonal distribution, and data completeness. To ensure robustness, sensors were classified according to predefined data quality criteria. Sensors with insufficient temporal coverage or limited seasonal representativeness were excluded from annual or inter-zone analyses and interpreted cautiously when included for descriptive purposes. Based on these criteria, 17 sensors were considered suitable for general descriptive analyses, 15 for annual pattern assessment, and 12 for robust inter-zone comparisons. This QA/QC framework ensured that subsequent analyses were based on representative and operationally reliable datasets while minimizing potential biases associated with uneven temporal coverage.

2.3 VOC Sampling and Processing

Targeted sampling campaigns were conducted to characterize volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and aldehydes across representative hospital environments during different operational and seasonal conditions. Sampling locations were selected to complement the continuous monitoring network and included common spaces, hospitalization wards, consultation areas, intensive care units, and pathological anatomy laboratories. VOC sampling was performed using active air collection on sorbent tubes, followed by thermal desorption and gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (TD-GC/MS) analysis [29]. Aldehydes, including formaldehyde, were collected using derivatization cartridges and analysed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) following established analytical procedures [30].

The analytical campaigns enabled the identification of pollutant-specific chemical signatures associated with different hospital activities and operational environments, including occupancy-related compounds, aldehydes, terpenes, siloxanes, and solvent-related emissions. These targeted measurements were subsequently integrated with continuous sensor observations to support the interpretation of temporal IAQ patterns and potential emission sources. In addition, indoor-to-outdoor (I/O) ratios were calculated by dividing indoor pollutant concentrations by the corresponding outdoor concentrations, allowing the differentiation between predominantly indoor and outdoor emission sources [31,32].

2.4 Microbiome Sampling and Processing

Airborne microbial samples were collected in selected hospital areas using a Coriolis cyclonic air sampler (Bertin Technologies), operating at a flow rate of 300 L/min. Bioaerosols were concentrated into sterile collection liquid for subsequent microbiological and molecular analyses. Air samples were analysed using culture-based methods and amplicon sequencing targeting bacterial (16S rRNA gene) and fungal (ITS region) markers to characterize airborne microbial communities across representative hospital

environments. DNA extraction, library preparation, sequencing, and bioinformatic processing were performed following established high-throughput sequencing workflows.

The resulting microbiological and microbiome datasets were used to provide complementary biological contextualization of the monitored IAQ conditions and to explore potential relationships between environmental parameters, occupancy conditions, and airborne microbial composition. Additional grouped analyses comparing controlled and non-controlled hospital environments were performed to evaluate the influence of occupancy and environmental management conditions on airborne microbial profiles.

2.5 Data processing and statistical analysis

2.5.1 Sensor data processing and quality control

Raw sensor datasets were processed using a reproducible Python-based workflow developed for harmonization, quality control, and temporal aggregation of the hospital IAQ monitoring data. Data pre-processing included timestamp normalization, duplicate removal, separation of indoor and outdoor measurements, consistency checks, and generation of hourly aggregated datasets. Sensor coverage and temporal representativeness were evaluated considering monitoring span, number of observations, hourly completeness, seasonal coverage, and percentage of valid measurements. Sensors with insufficient temporal coverage were excluded from analyses involving annual or seasonal pattern interpretation, while still being considered for descriptive contextualization when appropriate. The final processed dataset included continuous measurements of temperature, relative humidity, CO₂, PM_{2.5}, formaldehyde (CH₂O), and tVOCs collected across five hospital microenvironment typologies between June 2023 and December 2025.

2.5.2 Pollutant-specific IAQ assessment

Indoor air quality assessment was performed using a pollutant-specific adaptation of the GO AQS methodology. Continuous measurements of CO₂, PM_{2.5}, and formaldehyde were classified into “Good”, “Moderate”, and “Poor” IAQ categories according to predefined concentration thresholds derived from GO AQS recommendations and complementary IAQ reference values. For each pollutant and monitoring location, the percentage of time spent within each IAQ category was calculated together with exceedance frequencies, annual averages, and upper-tail exposure indicators (P90 concentrations). Time-resolved analyses included hourly profiles, monthly distributions, and seasonal heatmaps to identify recurrent pollutant accumulation periods and operational IAQ patterns. Because tVOC measurements were obtained using MOS-based sensors with different scaling phases during the monitoring campaign, tVOC data were interpreted qualitatively as relative indicators of volatile accumulation dynamics rather than quantitative measurements of specific compounds.

2.5.3 Integrated multi-pollutant assessment

To support operational interpretation of IAQ conditions, pollutant-specific classifications were combined into an integrated multi-parameter assessment framework. Rather than relying exclusively on average concentrations, the analysis considered the coexistence of recurrent exceedances across multiple pollutants and the temporal persistence of non-optimal IAQ conditions.

Overall IAQ interpretation was therefore based on the combined behaviour of occupancy-related indicators (CO₂), particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), and volatile pollutant indicators (formaldehyde and qualitative tVOC signals). This approach enabled the identification of pollutant-specific operational signatures and situations where acceptable occupancy-related ventilation conditions did not necessarily correspond to low chemical pollutant accumulation.

2.5.4 Pairing of continuous monitoring and targeted sampling

Continuous sensor measurements were temporally paired with targeted chemical and microbiological sampling campaigns to provide environmental context for the interpretation of discrete analytical observations. Pairing was performed at both area and sensor level using retrospective integration windows of 1 h, 3 h, and 24 h prior to each sampling event.

The paired datasets included pollutant concentrations, IAQ classification metrics, exceedance frequencies, temporal variability indicators, and contextual environmental variables. The 24 h integration window was primarily used for interpretation of chemical sampling campaigns due to its greater representativeness of short-term environmental conditions surrounding each targeted measurement.

The integrated analysis was subsequently used to explore the consistency between continuous monitoring signatures and targeted chemical or microbiological characterization across the different hospital environments.

2.6 Ethics

This study focused on environmental indoor air quality monitoring and targeted environmental sampling within hospital facilities. No personal data, clinical information, or patient interventions were involved in the study. All IAQ measurements were collected anonymously at room or area level without identification of individual occupants. According to institutional guidelines and the non-interventional nature of the work, formal ethical approval was not required.

3. Results

3.1. IAQ conditions and exposure overview across hospital areas

Indoor air quality (IAQ) conditions were first assessed using aggregated metrics and time-resolved exposure indicators derived from continuous sensor measurements. Table 1 summarizes data coverage, pollutant behaviour, and dominant IAQ patterns across the monitored hospital areas.

Overall, all areas were classified as “Good” according to aggregated concentration-based criteria. However, time-resolved analysis revealed substantial differences in exposure dynamics, variability, and dominant drivers. CO₂, used as a proxy for ventilation and occupancy, showed the greatest spatial variability. The ICU (HOS01003) maintained consistently low concentrations, with more than 98% of the time within the “Good” category, whereas outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004) showed lower “Good” proportions in specific locations, indicating recurrent ventilation limitations during occupancy peaks. PM_{2.5} concentrations were generally low, with most zones remaining within the “Good” category for more than 90% of the monitored time. Deviations were mainly episodic, suggesting transient particulate events rather than persistent particulate pollution. Formaldehyde showed the strongest temporal variability. Elevated levels were detected in several areas in 2023, with sustained Moderate conditions and occasional periods approaching Poor conditions. This pattern decreased markedly in 2024–2025, suggesting mitigation, changes in operational conditions, or reduction of transient emission sources.

Based on pollutant behaviour, temporal exposure, and spatial variability, distinct IAQ typologies were identified: stable controlled environments (ICU), event-driven areas linked to occupancy and ventilation demand, heterogeneous patient-room environments, and source-driven laboratory spaces. In several cases, annual mean concentrations remained within acceptable ranges despite recurrent upper-tail events or persistent non-optimal conditions during specific operational periods, highlighting the limitations of aggregated IAQ metrics alone.

These findings show that hospital areas with similar overall IAQ classifications may exhibit markedly different exposure dynamics, reinforcing the need for time-resolved analysis and multi-sensor deployment in complex healthcare environments.

Table 1. Summary of IAQ conditions, data coverage, and dominant patterns across hospital areas.

Zone /Area description	Sensors (n)	Data coverage	CO ₂ (Good %)	PM _{2.5} (Good %)	CH ₂ O (Good %)	Main IAQ driver	IAQ typology
HOS01001 / Common spaces and waiting areas	2	High (1 robust, 1 limited)	84–94%	>95%	81–98%	Occupancy /ventilation	Event-driven
HOS01002 / General hospitalization ward	8	High (most sensors robust)	75–90%	85–98%	13–95% (strong temporal variation)	Ventilation + chemical source	Heterogeneous / transient
HOS01003 / Intensive care unit	4	High (robust across sensors)	>98%	>98%	>95% (after 2023)	Controlled ventilation	Stable
HOS01004 / Outpatient consultation facilities	2	Moderate–high (some seasonal limitations)	53–95%	>90%	50–98% (improving over time)	Ventilation (occupancy-driven)	Strongly event-driven
HOS01005 / Pathological anatomy labs	2	High (robust coverage)	>95%	85–98%	65–98% (localized deviations)	Local emission sources	Source-driven

3.2. Temporal dynamics and exceedance patterns

3.2.1. Occupancy-driven CO₂ dynamics

Temporal analysis of CO₂ concentrations revealed clear occupancy-driven patterns across several hospital areas, particularly in common spaces, waiting areas, and hospitalization wards. In contrast, the intensive care unit (ICU) exhibited a markedly stable profile, consistent with continuous controlled ventilation and lower sensitivity to occupancy fluctuations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. (A) Common spaces and waiting rooms (HOS01001), showing clear occupancy-driven daytime peaks; (B) General hospitalization ward (HOS01002), characterized by more distributed and persistent exceedances associated with heterogeneous occupancy patterns; and (C) Intensive care ward (HOS01003), exhibiting stable CO₂ conditions with minimal temporal variability. Heatmaps represent the percentage of hourly sensor measurements outside the GO AQS “Good” category (>800 ppm) as a function of hour of day and monitoring period.

The strongest occupancy-related behaviour was observed in common spaces and outpatient consultation areas (HOS01001, figure 1A, and HOS01002), where recurrent daytime increases were detected during late morning and early afternoon periods. Heatmap analysis showed persistent exceedances of the GO IAQS “Good” threshold (>800 ppm) concentrated between approximately 10:00 and 15:00, particularly during autumn and summer periods. In the most affected cells, more than 40% of sensor-hours were outside the “Good” category, despite average concentrations remaining close to or below threshold values. This behaviour was more clearly reflected by the upper-tail distribution (P90) than by mean concentrations alone. Several occupancy-driven periods exhibited mean CO₂ concentrations below 800 ppm while simultaneously presenting P90 values exceeding 1100–1200 ppm, indicating recurrent high-exposure episodes affecting a substantial proportion of occupied periods. These findings suggest that average values alone may underestimate ventilation-related IAQ limitations in dynamic healthcare environments.

The hospitalization ward (HOS01002) showed a different temporal signature compared with common spaces. Rather than presenting concentrated occupancy peaks, CO₂ exceedances were more spatially distributed and temporally persistent throughout the

day (Figure 1B), reflecting the heterogeneous occupancy patterns and ventilation conditions of patient rooms. The most affected periods occurred during daytime hours, particularly around midday in winter, although exceedances remained less sharply defined than in waiting or consultation areas.

In contrast, the ICU (HOS01003) exhibited minimal CO₂ variability and very low exceedance frequencies throughout the study period (Figure 1C). Even during the most affected hourly cells, P90 values remained below the GO AQS “Good” threshold, confirming the effectiveness of dedicated ventilation strategies in maintaining stable IAQ conditions independently of occupancy variations.

Overall, CO₂ heatmaps revealed distinct operational ventilation signatures across hospital environments. High-occupancy areas exhibited predictable and recurrent daytime peaks, while controlled environments such as the ICU maintained stable profiles with negligible temporal variability. These findings support the use of continuous CO₂ monitoring not only as a ventilation adequacy indicator, but also as a practical tool for identifying operational windows where ventilation schedules or airflow strategies could be optimized.

3.2.2. Seasonal and room-dependent formaldehyde behaviour

Formaldehyde (CH₂O) exhibited markedly different temporal behaviour compared with CO₂, showing strong seasonal dependence, persistence during low-occupancy periods, and substantial variability between rooms within the same hospital area (**se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

Figure 2. Representative formaldehyde heatmaps illustrating distinct volatile accumulation behaviours across hospital microenvironments during summer conditions. (A) Intensive care ward

(HOS01003), characterized by stable background conditions with minimal temporal variability; (B) hospitalization ward room showing persistent formaldehyde accumulation patterns; and (C) outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004), exhibiting recurrent nighttime and early-morning exceedance events with marked temporal variability. Heatmaps represent hourly percentages of sensor measurements outside the GO AQS “Good” category ($>27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) as a function of hour of day and day of the week.

The most pronounced formaldehyde signals were observed in hospitalization wards and outpatient consultation areas, particularly during summer conditions. In contrast to CO_2 , elevated CH_2O levels were not concentrated during occupancy peaks, but frequently appeared during nighttime and early morning hours, suggesting the influence of temperature-dependent emissions, material off-gassing, or ventilation-related accumulation processes rather than direct human occupancy.

This behaviour was especially evident in specific patient rooms within the hospitalization ward (HOS01002), where heatmaps revealed two distinct temporal signatures. Some rooms exhibited persistent formaldehyde exceedances across extended periods and multiple hours of the day (Figure 2B), while others showed only episodic or intermittent events (Figure 2C). The coexistence of these different behaviours within the same ward highlights the importance of microenvironmental variability and suggests that local conditions may strongly influence formaldehyde dynamics.

The outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004) showed the strongest seasonal signal in the entire hospital dataset. Summer early-morning periods presented recurrent exceedances of the GO AQS “Good” threshold ($>27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with some hourly cells exceeding 50% of sensor-hours outside the “Good” category. In these cases, both mean concentrations and P90 values were simultaneously elevated, indicating sustained rather than purely episodic behaviour.

In contrast, the ICU environment (HOS01003) exhibited consistently low formaldehyde levels with minimal temporal variability (Figure 2A), reinforcing its role as a stable reference environment with effective ventilation control and limited pollutant accumulation.

The temporal characteristics observed for formaldehyde differed fundamentally from those of CO_2 , indicating that pollutant-specific IAQ dynamics must be considered when interpreting indoor air quality conditions. While CO_2 mainly reflected occupancy-driven ventilation demand, formaldehyde behaviour appeared more strongly associated with seasonal conditions, material emissions, and local environmental factors.

Overall, formaldehyde heatmaps demonstrated that aggregated concentration metrics alone may fail to capture relevant exposure patterns, particularly when recurrent upper-tail events occur during specific environmental conditions or within localized microenvironments.

3.2.3. $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ episodic behaviour and filtration-related patterns

Compared with CO_2 and formaldehyde, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exhibited weaker temporal structure and lower overall variability across the monitored hospital environments. Most areas remained within the GO AQS “Good” category for the majority of the monitoring period, with annual average concentrations generally below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Heatmap analysis revealed that particulate matter behaviour was predominantly episodic rather than persistent, with short-duration events appearing irregularly across different zones. Unlike CO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exceedances did not consistently follow occupancy-related schedules, and no strong recurrent daily patterns were identified. This suggests that particulate concentrations were influenced by localized activities, transient indoor processes, or occasional outdoor infiltration rather than sustained ventilation limitations.

The ICU (HOS01003) showed the lowest PM_{2.5} variability and exceedance frequency, consistent with the controlled ventilation and filtration systems operating in this environment. In contrast, occasional PM_{2.5} events were detected in outpatient consultation areas and laboratory environments, particularly in the paraffin dispensing area (HOS01005), where intermittent increases were observed during specific operational periods.

Although PM_{2.5} was not identified as the dominant IAQ concern in the studied hospital environments, the temporal analysis demonstrated the usefulness of continuous monitoring for detecting transient particulate events that may not be captured through aggregated concentration metrics alone. These findings also suggest that filtration performance and localized emission sources may play a more relevant role than occupancy dynamics in shaping PM_{2.5} temporal behaviour within healthcare environments.

3.2.4. Distinct operational IAQ signatures across hospital environments

Comparison of hourly pollutant profiles revealed the presence of distinct operational IAQ signatures across hospital environments, reflecting differences in occupancy patterns, ventilation strategies, and local emission sources (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Representative hourly IAQ operational profiles across distinct hospital microenvironments. (A) Intensive care ward (HOS01003) showing stable CO₂ behaviour with minimal divergence between mean and upper-tail concentrations; (B) outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004) exhibiting pronounced occupancy-driven CO₂ peaks and increased percentages of hours outside the GO IAQS “Good” category during daytime periods; (C) hospitalization ward room with persistent formaldehyde elevations; and (D) pathological anatomy laboratory showing source-driven formaldehyde behaviour associated with operational activities. Profiles include mean, median, P90 concentrations, and percentage of hours outside the GO IAQS “Good” category.

Controlled environments such as the intensive care unit (HOS01003) exhibited highly stable CO₂ behaviour throughout the day, with minimal divergence between mean, median, and P90 concentrations and negligible percentages of hours outside the GO AQs “Good” category (Figure 3A). These results indicate effective ventilation performance and limited temporal variability, confirming the role of the ICU as a stable reference environment within the hospital.

In contrast, outpatient consultation and waiting areas (HOS01004) showed pronounced occupancy-driven CO₂ dynamics characterized by recurrent daytime peaks between late morning and early afternoon (Figure 3B). During these periods, the divergence between mean and P90 concentrations increased substantially, accompanied by a marked rise in the percentage of hours outside the “Good” category. These findings indicate recurrent short-term ventilation limitations associated with occupancy peaks that are not fully reflected by daily average concentrations alone.

Hospitalization wards (HOS01002) exhibited a markedly different formaldehyde profile compared with occupancy-driven CO₂ behaviour. Some rooms showed persistent formaldehyde elevations across extended periods of the day, with sustained increases in both P90 concentrations and percentages of hours outside the “Good” category (Figure 3C). This behaviour suggests the presence of localized and relatively continuous emission sources rather than isolated occupancy-related events.

Laboratory environments (HOS01005) displayed another distinct IAQ signature characterized by relatively stable CO₂ conditions combined with localized formaldehyde increases associated with operational activities (Figure 4D). In these spaces, pollutant dynamics appeared to be primarily linked to process-related emissions and material handling rather than occupant density or general ventilation demand.

Overall, the comparison of representative hourly profiles demonstrated that hospital IAQ behaviour cannot be adequately characterized using aggregated concentration metrics alone. Instead, pollutant-specific temporal signatures provide more detailed information regarding ventilation adequacy, occupancy effects, and local emission processes. These operational signatures may therefore support the identification of environment-specific IAQ management strategies adapted to the characteristics and functional use of each hospital area. These findings support the concept of pollutant-specific operational IAQ signatures, where temporal pollutant behaviour reflects the functional characteristics, ventilation strategy, and dominant emission processes of each hospital microenvironment.

3.3. VOCs and Aldehydes Characterization

3.3.1. Spatial chemical characterization across hospital environments

Targeted chemical sampling revealed clear differences in pollutant composition and VOC signatures across the monitored hospital environments, reflecting the influence of occupancy, ventilation conditions, and local emission sources. Detailed analytical results are presented elsewhere in the companion chemical characterization study; however, several findings were directly relevant for the interpretation of the continuous IAQ monitoring results obtained in the present work.

The pathological anatomy laboratory exhibited the most differentiated chemical profile among the monitored areas, characterized by elevated concentrations of aldehydes and solvent-related compounds associated with laboratory operational activities and material handling processes. Formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, acetone, and aromatic compounds such as xylenes and ethylbenzene were recurrently detected in this environment, supporting the existence of process-related emission sources. In contrast, the intensive care unit (ICU) consistently exhibited the lowest VOC burden, in agreement with the stable temporal behaviour observed through continuous sensor monitoring.

Hospitalization wards and outpatient consultation areas exhibited more heterogeneous VOC profiles, including aldehydes, terpenes, siloxanes, and occupancy-related compounds associated with cleaning products, human activity, and ventilation variability. Seasonal variability was also observed for several compounds, particularly aldehydes, with higher concentrations generally detected during warmer periods.

Principal component analysis performed in the companion study showed clear separation between laboratory environments and the remaining hospital areas, supporting the existence of differentiated chemical microenvironments within the hospital building. Overall, the targeted sampling campaigns confirmed that different hospital environments exhibited pollutant-specific chemical signatures associated with their operational use, ventilation conditions, and local emission sources. The 10 main compounds identified across hospital environments are summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Indoor-to-outdoor (I/O) ratios of the 10 most relevant volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and aldehydes in terms of indoor concentration across different hospital areas. Colors indicate source attribution: red ($I/O \approx 1 \pm 0.5$, outdoor-dominated), blue ($1.5 < I/O < 10$, mixed indoor–outdoor sources), and green ($I/O > 10$, indoor-dominated). Cells without color indicate that the compound was not detected in the corresponding sampling location.

3.3.2. Consistency between targeted sampling and continuous monitoring

Pairing of discrete sampling campaigns with continuous sensor data provided additional temporal and operational context for the interpretation of the observed IAQ patterns. Retrospective 1 h, 3 h, and 24 h windows were evaluated, with the 24 h integration period providing the most representative environmental context for comparison with targeted chemical measurements.

The temporal behaviour identified by the continuous monitoring network showed strong qualitative consistency with the pollutant signatures observed during the targeted sampling campaigns. Areas exhibiting stable sensor profiles and low temporal variability, such as the ICU, also presented the lowest VOC burdens. Conversely, laboratory areas displaying source-driven formaldehyde dynamics in the continuous monitoring analysis also showed elevated concentrations of aldehydes and solvent-related compounds during targeted sampling campaigns.

Hospitalization wards provided one of the clearest examples of the complementarity between both approaches. Continuous monitoring identified persistent formaldehyde elevations and substantial room-to-room variability, while targeted chemical analysis confirmed the presence of heterogeneous aldehyde and VOC compositions across these environments. Similarly, occupancy-driven CO_2 dynamics observed in waiting and

consultation areas were coherent with the presence of VOCs commonly associated with human activity, cleaning products, and indoor occupancy.

Although direct quantitative equivalence between sensor variables and analytical measurements was not expected, particularly for tVOC metrics and particle measurements, the integration of both approaches provided coherent and complementary information regarding pollutant sources, temporal behaviour, and operational IAQ signatures.

These results suggest that continuous sensor networks may provide valuable temporal context for discrete chemical and microbiological sampling campaigns, facilitating the interpretation of recurrent exposure scenarios and improving the operational understanding of IAQ dynamics in healthcare environments. The main relationships identified between targeted chemical characterization and continuous monitoring signatures across the studied hospital environments are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Representative relationships between targeted sampling and continuous monitoring across hospital environments.

Hospital area / typology	Main findings from targeted sampling	Continuous monitoring signature	Main interpreted IAQ driver
HOS01003 – Intensive Care Unit (ICU)	Lowest overall VOC burden and most homogeneous chemical composition. Reduced presence of aldehydes and occupancy-related compounds.	Stable CO ₂ , PM _{2.5} and CH ₂ O profiles with minimal temporal variability and very low percentages of hours outside the GO AQS “Good” category.	Controlled ventilation and filtration systems.
HOS01001 / HOS01004 – Common spaces, waiting and consultation areas	Presence of occupancy-related VOCs, including terpenes, siloxanes, and compounds associated with human activity and cleaning products.	Recurrent daytime CO ₂ peaks concentrated during occupancy hours, with clear divergence between mean and P90 concentrations during peak periods.	Occupancy-driven ventilation demand.
HOS01002 – Hospitalization ward	Heterogeneous VOC and aldehyde composition between rooms, including variable formaldehyde-related signatures.	Persistent and spatially heterogeneous CH ₂ O behaviour with substantial room-to-room variability and recurrent exceedances in selected rooms.	Localized emission sources combined with heterogeneous occupancy and ventilation conditions.
HOS01005 – Pathological anatomy laboratories	Elevated aldehydes and solvent-related compounds associated with laboratory activities and material handling processes.	Source-driven formaldehyde behaviour and episodic PM _{2.5} events associated with operational periods.	Process- and material-related emissions.

3.3.3. Decoupling between occupancy-related ventilation indicators and chemical accumulation

Representative hourly profiles revealed recurrent situations in which occupancy-related ventilation indicators suggested acceptable IAQ conditions while volatile pollutant accumulation remained elevated (Figure 5). The clearest examples were observed in outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004) during summer periods, where CO₂ P90 concentrations remained below the GO IAQS “Good” threshold (<800 ppm) and less than 5% of hours were outside the “Good” category, while formaldehyde P90 concentrations exceeded 100 µg/m³ and more than 50% of hours remained outside the “Good” category.

Figure 5. Representative examples of decoupling between occupancy-related ventilation indicators and volatile pollutant accumulation during summer conditions. (A) Hospitalization ward (HOS01002) showing recurrent periods with moderate CO₂ concentrations and limited percentages of hours outside the GO AQS “Good” category, while formaldehyde concentrations and relative tVOC signals remained elevated during early morning and nighttime periods; and (B) outpatient consultation facilities (HOS01004), exhibiting the strongest decoupling behaviour observed in the study, with formaldehyde P90 concentrations exceeding the GO IAQS “Good” threshold despite CO₂ concentrations remaining predominantly below 800 ppm. tVOC signals are represented as relative indicators of elevated volatile accumulation ($\geq P75$ within each zone and tVOC scaling phase) and are interpreted qualitatively rather than as quantitative measurements of specific compounds.

Similar behaviour was identified in hospitalization wards (HOS01002), particularly during summer early-morning and nighttime periods, where elevated formaldehyde and relative tVOC signals occurred despite moderate CO₂ concentrations. These results indicate that occupancy-related ventilation indicators alone may not fully capture volatile pollutant accumulation dynamics in healthcare environments.

The combined interpretation of CO₂, formaldehyde, and qualitative tVOC signals therefore provided complementary operational information regarding ventilation effectiveness and pollutant accumulation. While CO₂ primarily reflected occupancy-driven ventilation demand, formaldehyde and tVOC signals frequently revealed persistent or source-related chemical accumulation patterns not directly associated with occupancy peaks.

These findings support the use of multi-parameter sensor networks for operational IAQ assessment in complex indoor environments. In particular, the integration of occupancy indicators with qualitative volatile pollutant monitoring may improve the identification of recurrent chemical accumulation scenarios and facilitate more targeted ventilation management strategies.

3.4. Microbiological characterization

Integrated microbiological analyses revealed a high degree of airborne microbial homogenization across the monitored hospital environments. No significant spatial differences were identified in either bacterial or fungal community composition between hospital subzones or between hospital and control environments, suggesting the existence of relatively conserved airborne microbial cores throughout the hospital building. In contrast, bacterial communities showed a significant association with seasonality, indicating

that temporal environmental variability represented a stronger driver of airborne microbial composition than spatial compartmentalization within the monitored hospital areas.

Richness analyses additionally supported this homogenization pattern, with no significant differences observed in bacterial or fungal richness among the monitored hospital environments. Similarly, taxonomic occurrence analyses showed complete overlap of detected bacterial and fungal genera across all sampled locations, with no exclusive taxa associated with any individual hospital area.

Despite this overall microbiological homogenization, differences associated with occupancy influence and environmental control were identified. Non-controlled areas such as corridors and waiting rooms exhibited significantly higher relative abundances of Gram-positive bacteria compared with controlled environments, suggesting a stronger contribution of occupancy-associated microbial sources in highly transited hospital spaces (Figure 8). In contrast, controlled areas such as ICUs and selected hospitalization environments exhibited lower relative abundances, consistent with more stable ventilation and environmental control conditions. These findings were coherent with the occupancy-driven CO₂ dynamics identified through continuous monitoring in waiting and consultation areas and further supported the influence of human presence and space use intensity on airborne environmental composition.

Figure 8. Relative abundance of Gram-positive bacteria in controlled and non-controlled hospital environments. Non-controlled areas exhibited significantly higher Gram-positive abundance, suggesting stronger occupancy-associated microbial influence in highly transited hospital spaces (Wilcoxon test, $p = 0.012$).

Overall, the microbiological characterization reinforced the importance of temporal and occupancy-related dynamics in shaping hospital IAQ conditions. The integration of microbiological analyses with continuous IAQ monitoring and targeted chemical characterization therefore provided complementary information supporting a more comprehensive interpretation of environmental behaviour and operational exposure scenarios across the monitored hospital environments.

4. Discussion

4.1 Dynamic and pollutant-specific IAQ behaviour in healthcare environments

The results of this study highlight the importance of time-resolved IAQ assessment for understanding pollutant behaviour in complex healthcare environments. Although average concentrations frequently remained within acceptable IAQ ranges, detailed temporal analyses revealed recurrent short-term exposure events, seasonal accumulation

patterns, and pollutant-specific operational behaviours that would have remained masked using aggregated metrics alone.

The monitored hospital microenvironments exhibited clearly differentiated pollutant dynamics associated with occupancy patterns, ventilation conditions, and local emission sources. CO₂ showed strong occupancy-related temporal signatures, especially in waiting and consultation areas characterized by fluctuating ventilation demand. In contrast, formaldehyde displayed more persistent accumulation dynamics in selected hospitalization rooms and laboratory-associated spaces, suggesting the influence of continuous indoor emission sources and reduced nighttime air renewal. PM_{2.5} concentrations generally remained low and stable, although localized short-term peaks were identified in selected operational areas.

These findings demonstrate that different IAQ parameters capture complementary aspects of indoor environmental quality and should not be interpreted interchangeably. While CO₂ primarily reflects occupancy-related ventilation adequacy, volatile compounds and aldehydes provide additional information regarding indoor emissions, cleaning activities, and pollutant accumulation processes not directly associated with occupancy intensity. Several monitored spaces exhibited acceptable CO₂ concentrations while simultaneously showing persistent formaldehyde elevations and volatile accumulation patterns, indicating that occupancy-related indicators alone may not fully represent IAQ conditions in healthcare environments.

The integration of continuous monitoring with targeted chemical characterization substantially improved the interpretation of pollutant dynamics across the monitored areas. Stable sensor profiles observed in the ICU were coherent with the low VOC burden and homogeneous chemical composition identified through targeted sampling, whereas laboratory and hospitalization areas exhibiting recurrent formaldehyde accumulation also showed differentiated aldehyde and solvent-related chemical signatures. Together, these results support the concept that IAQ conditions in hospitals should be interpreted as dynamic and multidimensional phenomena rather than as isolated concentration measurements.

4.2 Implications for adaptive ventilation management and hospital BMS operation

The results obtained in this study demonstrate the potential of continuous multi-parameter IAQ monitoring to support more adaptive and operationally oriented ventilation management strategies in healthcare environments. Beyond their use as descriptive monitoring tools, the deployed sensor networks provided high temporal resolution information capable of identifying recurrent pollutant accumulation periods, occupancy-driven ventilation demand, localized emission events, and pollutant-specific operational behaviours across different hospital microenvironments.

The observed temporal signatures suggest that different hospital areas may require differentiated ventilation management approaches depending on their dominant IAQ drivers. Waiting and consultation areas were characterized primarily by occupancy-related CO₂ dynamics, indicating that these spaces may benefit from demand-controlled ventilation strategies responsive to fluctuating occupancy conditions. In contrast, hospitalization rooms and laboratory-associated spaces exhibited more persistent volatile pollutant accumulation patterns, suggesting that occupancy-based ventilation control alone may be insufficient in environments influenced by continuous indoor emission sources or operational activities.

These findings support the transition from static ventilation approaches toward more flexible IAQ management frameworks integrating multiple environmental indicators simultaneously. The combined interpretation of CO₂, formaldehyde, PM_{2.5}, and qualitative TVOC signals may allow building management systems (BMS) to better distinguish between overcrowding events, ventilation limitations, transient operational activities, and persistent chemical accumulation scenarios. The recurrent temporal patterns identified through heatmaps and hourly profiles additionally suggest the potential for predictive and preventive IAQ management strategies, including ventilation schedule optimization, anomaly detection, and prioritization of corrective actions in sensitive hospital areas.

Overall, the findings support the concept that continuous multi-parameter IAQ monitoring may serve as a practical foundation for next-generation hospital IAQ management systems combining occupancy indicators with pollutant-specific environmental information to implement more adaptive, exposure-oriented, and operationally efficient ventilation strategies.

4.3 Integrated IAQ monitoring frameworks for healthcare environments

The present study highlights the value of combining continuous sensor monitoring with targeted chemical and biological characterization for IAQ assessment in complex healthcare environments. While each methodological approach independently provides useful environmental information, their integration enabled a more comprehensive interpretation of pollutant dynamics, operational IAQ patterns, and potential exposure scenarios across the monitored hospital microenvironments.

Continuous monitoring provided the temporal resolution necessary to identify recurrent pollutant accumulation periods, occupancy-driven ventilation demand, seasonal variability, and short-term operational events that would have been difficult to capture through isolated sampling campaigns alone. In parallel, targeted VOC and aldehyde characterization provided contextual information regarding pollutant composition and dominant emission sources associated with different hospital activities, substantially improving the interpretation of qualitative TVOC signals and recurrent volatile accumulation patterns. Complementary microbiological analyses additionally reinforced the influence of occupancy and temporal variability on airborne environmental conditions, supporting the interpretation of hospital IAQ as a dynamic and operationally driven phenomenon.

From an operational perspective, the proposed framework aligns closely with emerging IAQ 4.0 concepts, where continuous environmental monitoring supports actionable building management, adaptive ventilation strategies, and exposure-oriented environmental control. Importantly, the methodology presented in this study was implemented using commercially available monitoring technologies and reproducible analytical workflows under real hospital operating conditions, supporting its practical applicability within healthcare environments.

4.4 Limitations and future work

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of this study. First, the monitoring strategy relied primarily on commercially available low-cost sensor (LCS) devices operating under real hospital conditions. Although these technologies provide important advantages in terms of scalability, temporal resolution, and

operational deployment, they also present known limitations related to sensor drift, environmental sensitivity, cross-interferences, and reduced analytical specificity compared with reference-grade instrumentation. Consequently, the results should be interpreted primarily from a temporal and operational perspective rather than as high-precision analytical measurements.

Particular caution is required when interpreting TVOC measurements. Changes in sensor scaling and firmware implementation during the monitoring campaign limited direct quantitative comparability across the entire study period. For this reason, TVOC data were interpreted qualitatively as indicators of volatile accumulation dynamics rather than as quantitative measurements of total VOC concentrations. Nevertheless, the integration of targeted chemical characterization substantially improved the contextual interpretation of these signals.

Another limitation relates to the spatial representativeness of the monitoring network. Although multiple hospital microenvironments were included over an extended monitoring period, some areas were represented by a limited number of sensors or exhibited lower temporal coverage. To minimize potential biases, a dedicated QA/QC and sensor coverage assessment framework was applied, and sensors with insufficient temporal representativeness were excluded from selected analyses.

The targeted chemical and microbiological campaigns additionally represented discrete snapshots of environmental conditions and therefore could not fully capture the complete temporal variability of pollutant composition or airborne microbial dynamics. While pairing these campaigns with continuous monitoring substantially improved contextual interpretation, future studies incorporating higher-frequency chemical characterization and continuous biological monitoring approaches may further strengthen the understanding of hospital IAQ dynamics.

Future work should additionally explore the integration of continuous IAQ monitoring with real-time BMS operation and adaptive ventilation control strategies. The recurrent temporal patterns identified in this study suggest that predictive and exposure-oriented ventilation management approaches may be feasible using multi-parameter IAQ datasets combined with machine learning techniques, anomaly detection algorithms, and predictive occupancy modelling.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the value of combining continuous multi-parameter IAQ monitoring with targeted chemical characterization for understanding pollutant dynamics and exposure conditions in complex healthcare environments. The results revealed substantial spatial and temporal heterogeneity across hospital microenvironments, with pollutant-specific behaviours strongly influenced by occupancy patterns, ventilation conditions, and local emission sources.

CO₂ concentrations were primarily associated with occupancy-driven ventilation demand, whereas formaldehyde and VOC-related indicators frequently exhibited more persistent accumulation patterns independent of occupancy intensity. These findings highlight that occupancy-based indicators alone may not fully represent IAQ conditions in healthcare environments and reinforce the importance of integrated multi-parameter monitoring approaches.

The combination of continuous monitoring with targeted VOC and aldehyde characterization substantially improved the interpretation of temporal sensor signals and

recurrent pollutant accumulation scenarios. Distinct operational IAQ signatures were identified across different hospital typologies, including occupancy-driven spaces, highly controlled environments such as the ICU, and process-related laboratory areas characterized by persistent aldehyde and solvent emissions.

From an operational perspective, the results support the transition from static IAQ assessment approaches toward more dynamic and exposure-oriented environmental management frameworks. Continuous monitoring networks provided valuable temporal information capable of identifying recurrent pollutant accumulation periods, ventilation limitations, and pollutant-specific operational behaviours that would have remained masked using aggregated metrics alone.

Overall, the study demonstrates that continuous multi-parameter IAQ monitoring implemented using commercially available technologies can provide a practical foundation for future adaptive hospital IAQ management strategies integrated with Building Management Systems (BMS). By combining occupancy indicators with pollutant-specific environmental information, these approaches may contribute to smarter, more preventive, and more health-oriented management of healthcare indoor environments.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/doi/s1>, Figure S1: title; Table S1: title; Video S1: title.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
DOAJ	Directory of open access journals
TLA	Three letter acronym
LD	Linear dichroism

Appendix A

Appendix A.1

The appendix is an optional section that can contain details and data supplemental to the main text—for example, explanations of experimental details that would disrupt the flow of the main text but nonetheless remain crucial to understanding and reproducing the research shown; figures of replicates for experiments of which representative data is shown in the main text can be added here if brief, or as Supplementary data. Mathematical proofs of results not central to the paper can be added as an appendix.

Table A1. This is a table caption.

Title 1	Title 2	Title 3
entry 1	data	data
entry 2	data	data

Appendix B

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References

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